

The search for relevance in Erwin Schrodinger's mutations and mathematical interlude from his book "What is Life?" to COVID-19 mutations and variants.

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Abstract

Erwin Schrodinger's book "What is Life?" describes mutations and formulates an equation for the time of expectation of mutation(t) in terms of Delbruck ratio (W/KT) where W is the lift, K , Boltzmann constant, T , absolute temperature, and a constant. Time of expectation of mutation (t) based on Delbruck ratio (DR) of 30 to 60 at $\tau = 10^{-14}$ sec is estimated and correlated from the coronavirus outbreak to the omicron variant's appearance. Delbruck ratio of 30 is considered for the start of coronavirus outbreak corresponding to t value of 0.10 sec. The declaration of the pandemic after three months by the World Health Organization (WHO) corresponds to a Delbruck ratio of 48.1 Between the ninth and the twenty-third month, five variants from alpha to omicron were reported corresponding to the Delbruck ratio of 49.1 and 50.15. The large initial difference of 18.1 and later of 2.01 in the Delbruck ratio for the appearance of variants is interpreted by the insights given in the book "What is Life?". The reported premise of a diminished t and increased mutability with a rise in temperature for fly *Drosophila*. is extended to delta and other variants.

Keywords : quantum , latent, mutations, discontinuity, intermediate,

1.0 Introduction

Professor Roger Penrose, in a foreword to Erwin Schrodinger's iconic book, has these lines "This serves to emphasize the continuing relevance that Schrodinger's "What is Life?" has for us today. It is amply worth rereading". The forward is dated 8th August 1991 for the preface of the 1992 edition of "What is Life?" first published in September 1944 (Schrodinger, 1992). This book influenced Crick and Watson to apply their rigorous intuition for the double helix of DNA (Sigmund 2019). This book does not mention mutations related to the flu pandemic of 1918 -1920. While reading this book in the present COVID 19 times, relevant lines appear.. "Schrodinger's "What is life "? has a mathematical interlude with an equation to estimate the time of expectation of mutation (t) in relation to Delbruck ratio (DR) and a small constant τ in sec. A search for the relevance of this mathematical interlude to present COVID 91 mutations and variants is presented. The findings are correlated from the coronavirus outbreak to the appearance of the omicron variant

2:0 Mathematical interlude as in the book : (Chapter 4, Page 51-52)

2.1 An equation for the time of expectation of mutation ($t = \tau e^{W/KT}$)

Schrodinger uses the work of Polanyi and Wigner (Polyani 1928) to explain the time of expectation of mutation (t). Here are the lines verbatim from the book. "From an investigation, due to M. Polanyi and E. Wigner, the 'time of expectation' largely depends on the ratio of two energies, one being just the energy difference itself that is required to effect the lift (let us write W for it), the other one characterizing the intensity of the heat motion at the temperature in question (let us write T for the absolute temperature and KT for the characteristic energy). It stands to reason that the chance for effecting the lift is smaller, and hence that the time of expectation is longer, the higher the lift itself compared with the average heat energy, that is to say, the greater the ratio $W:KT$. What is amazing is how enormously the time of expectation depends on comparatively small changes of the ratio $W:KT$. To give an example (following Delbriick): for W 30 times KT , the time of expectation might be as short as 1/10 sec but would rise to 16 months when W is 50 times KT , and to 30,000 years when W is 60 times KT ". Details about Max Delbruck and his achievements are available here (Golomb 1982). "Following Delbruck" is considered as Delbruck ratio (W/KT in this article).

“It might be as well to point out in mathematical language - for those readers to whom it appeals - the reason for this enormous sensitivity to changes in the level step or temperature and to add a few physical remarks of a similar kind. The reason is that the time of expectation, call it t , depends on the ratio W/KT by an exponential function, thus

$$t = \tau e^{W/KT} \quad (1)$$

where t = time of expectation, secs , τ = small constant 10^{-13} to 10^{-14} second”. K is Boltzmann constant. W is the lift. T = absolute temperature.

An example of $W/KT = 30$ is given special consideration on Page 52 of the book . It goes like this “Actually, a $W = 30 K T$ is already extremely rare. That it does not yet lead to an enormously long time of expectation (only 1/10 sec in our example) is, of course, due to the smallness of the factor . This factor has a physical meaning. It is of the order of the period of the vibrations which take place in the system all the time. You could, very broadly, describe this factor as meaning that the chance of accumulating the required amount W , though very small, recurs again and again 'at every vibration', that is to say, about 10^{13} or 10^{14} times during every second.”.

2.2 Temperature effect on mutability

In Chapter 5, on page 64 Schrodinger writes “ This enables us to test our mutability formula, which as written before was

$$t = \tau e^{W/KT} \quad (1)$$

(It will be remembered that t is the time of expectation for a mutation with threshold energy W .) We ask: How does t change with the temperature? We easily find from the preceding formula in good approximation the ratio of the value at temperature $T + 10$ to that at temperature T .

$$\frac{t_{T+10}}{t_T} = e^{-10W/KT^2} \quad (2)$$

The exponent being now negative, in equation (2) the ratio is, naturally, smaller than 1. The time of expectation is diminished by raising the temperature, the mutability is increased. Now that can be tested and has been tested with the fly *Drosophila* in the range of temperature which

the insects will stand”. The conclusions presented are **“temperature influences unstable genes less than stable ones .**

3.0 Discussion of 2.1 : in search of relevance to COVID 19 mutations & variants

Schrodinger clearly states in 2.2 (marked in bold) that t is the time of expectation of mutation. Therefore in this presentation, the time of expectation of mutation (t) estimated from equation (1) using Delbruck ratio from 30 to 50 is presented in Table 1. Since this is search for relevance in Schrodinger's mutations to COVID 19 times, a restriction in using the Delbruck ratio to the first decimal place is considered for this article. Those interested can insert the Delbruck ratio for more decimal places (for example, 30.11, 30.111, 30.1111 (or as many combinations possible for 30 to 50) and do elaborate computational estimations. The time of expectation of mutation (0.1 sec) for a Delbruck ratio of 30 is obtained, similar to the value reported in the book. However, for a Delbruck ratio of 50 and 60, different values are obtained from the values mentioned in the book(See Table 2).

Note that the sign for vibrations per sec has a positive 10^{13} and 10^{14} , whereas equation (1) the small constant is 10^{-13} to 10^{-14} sec. The interesting words are "10¹³ or 10¹⁴ times during every second". To interpret this, we move forward with different Delbruck ratios as presented in Table 1. The comparison between values in the book and the present work is given in Table 2. The lift (W) is the variable with K, Boltzmann constant, T temperature in Kelvin not exactly constant. However, there will be an average temperature at which mutations take place. The concerning aspect is the recurring accumulation of W at 10^{13} and 10^{14} times every second. The question is, "Does this 10^{13} and 10^{14} times vibration every second remain constant for the three Delbruck ratios used to estimate time of expectation of mutation (t) in Table 1?. If this large vibration per second applies to all "t" to be exponential, then the speed of the mutants and their variants moving around in the atmosphere would be phenomenal.

The time of expectation of mutation (t) at the start of the coronavirus outbreak (December 2019) at Wuhan, China, is considered as 0.10 secs, and the pandemic declaration on March 11, 2020, corresponding to 3.11 months [Table 1 & 3] (Zhu ,Wei and Pine 2020; Cucinotta and Vanelli 2020)). At the outbreak, the Delbruck ratio is 30, and at the declaration of pandemic @ 3.11 months, it is 48.14. Then all the variants are detected in a narrow range of Delbruck ratio between 48.14 and 50.15. The Delbruck ratio, as explained in the book, is sensitive

between 30 and 50 and from 50 to 60, t stretches to years. The question is, "Were there several mutants between 0.10 secs and 3.11 months?. For this, examining lines from Section of 2.1. is initiated. The lines are as follows "It stands to reason that the chance for effecting the lift is smaller, and hence the time of expectation is longer, the higher the lift itself compared with the average heat energy, that is to say, the greater the ratio $W:KT$." Lift is considered as threshold energy (See section 2.2). A question for experts. "Does significant increase of $W:KT$ by 18.14 {(30 to 48.14 in Table 3)} between the outbreak and declaration of pandemic result in lift (W), the threshold energy being higher than the average heat energy? If the lift was higher with a significant increase in Delbruck ratio of $W:KT$ (18.14), were mutants roaming globally during this period at 10^{13} or 10^{14} vibrations per second. At a higher time of expectation of mutation (t) [3.11 to 23 months, Table 1] , Delbruck ratio is between 48.14 to 50.15 (difference =2.01).

Does this difference in low Delbruck ratio (2.01) signify the slowest step (the rate determining step) for building up Schrodinger's quantum anxiety of " infecting the human race with unwanted latent mutations?". (See Table 3 for list of variants from latent mutations). The above underlined statement is taken from Page 45 of the book. Here are two statements analysed to justify the term quantum anxiety. ” “It is not a point that need worry any individual personally. But any possibility of gradually infecting the human race with unwanted latent mutations ought to be a matter of concern to the community." There are no intermediate lines between “It is not a point that need worry any individual personally” and infecting the human race with unwanted latent mutations ". This is analogous to Schrodinger's description of quantum physics having no intermediate energies between energy levels. Schrodinger applies this to De Vries discontinuous mutations as quantum theory of biology.

There is a lesson to be learned from $t = 0.10$ secs to 3.11 months. Schrodinger's premise of lift (threshold energy) exceeding average heat energy with a significant increase in Delbruck ratio (18.14) should be avoided for a pandemic to result for a long duration as the present COVID 19 one. Therefore, a pandemic should be declared at an early t within seconds. The origin of outbreak of the virus should be isolated as fast as possible from the rest of the world till an all clear is given by a recognised international body for re-connecting globally.

Table 1 : Data on t, time expectation of mutation in secs, minutes, hours,,days , months & years by equation (1) with respect to W/KT (Delbruck ratio) with $\tau=10^{-14}$ sec

W/KT	1E-14	t (secs)	t(mins)	t(hrs)	t (days)	t (months)	t (years)
30		0.1069					
31		0.290488					
32		0.78963					
33		2.146436					
34		5.834617					
35		15.86013					
36		43.11232					
37		117.1914	1.95319				
38		318.5593	5.309322				
39		865.934	14.43223				
40		2353.853	39.23088				
41		6398.435	106.6406	1.777343			
42		17392.75	289.8792	4.831319			
43		47278.39	787.9732	13.13289			
44		128516	2141.933	35.69889	1.487454		
45		349342.7	5822.379	97.03964	4.043318		
46		949611.9	15826.87	263.7811	10.99088		
47		2581313	43021.88	717.0314	29.87631		
48		7016736	116945.6	1949.093	81.21222	2.707074	
48.1		7754692	129244.9	2154.081	89.75339	2.99178	
48.14		8071167	134519.5	2241.991	93.41629	3.1139	
48.2		8570261	142837.7	2380.628	99.19283	3.306428	
49		19073466	317891.1	5298.185	220.7577	7.35859	
49.2		23296384	388273.1	6471.218	269.6341	8.987802	
49.21		23530516	392175.3	6536.254	272.3439	9.0781	
49.5		31446829	524113.8	8735.23	363.9679	12.13	
49.7		38409243	640154.1	10669.23	444.5514	14.81838	
49.8		42448779	707479.6	11791.33	491.3053	16.37684	
49.9		46913156	781885.9	13031.43	542.9763	18.09921	
50		51847055	864117.6	14401.96	600.0817	20.00272	1.666893
50.1		57299858	954997.6	15916.63	663.1928	22.10643	1.842202
50.15		59638309	993971.8	16566.2	690.2582	23.009	1.917384
50.2		63326136	1055436	17590.59	732.9414	24.43138	2.035948
50.3		69986204	1166437	19440.61	810.0255	27.00085	2.250071
50.4		77346718	1289112	21485.2	895.2166	29.84055	2.486713
51		1.41E+08	2348915	39148.59	1631.191	54.37304	4.531086
52		3.83E+08	6385013	106416.9	4434.037	147.8012	12.31677
53		1.04E+09	17356266	289271.1	12052.96	401.7654	33.48045
54		2.83E+09	47179222	786320.4	32763.35	1092.112	91.0093
55		7.69E+09	1.28E+08	2137440	89060.01	2968.667	247.3889
56		2.09E+10	3.49E+08	5810165	242090.2	8069.674	672.4728
57		5.69E+10	9.48E+08	15793667	658069.4	21935.65	1827.971
58		1.55E+11	2.58E+09	42931637	1788818	59627.27	4968.939
59		4.2E+11	7E+09	1.17E+08	4862512	162083.7	13506.98
59.8		9.35E+11	1.56E+10	2.6E+08	10821720	360724	30060.33
60		1.14E+12	1.9E+10	3.17E+08	13217678	440589.3	36715.77

Table 2 Comparison of t , time of expectation of mutation(secs. days, months , years) as in the book with the present work done on Microsoft excel

Delbruck ratio W/KT	$t = \tau e^{W/KT}$ (present work)	$t = \tau e^{W/KT}$ (as in the book)
30	0.1068 secs	0.10 secs
49.8	16.38 months	
50	20.00 months	16 months
59.8	30060 years	
60	36716 years	30000 years

Table 3 The journey of COVID 2019 and its variants with respect to Delbruck ratio (W/KT) and time of expectation of mutation (t)

Start of COVID 19 Pandemic declaration Variants	Month/ Year start Pandemic declaration Detection. Of variants	Country of detecting variants./ International health Body in a country declaring the pandemic	t, time of expectation of mutation by equation (1) first row in secs and rest in months.(From Table 1)	Corresponding Delbruck ratio to time ‘t’ as in Table(1) marked in Arial Black
COVID 19 (start)	December 2019	Wuhan China Zhu et al (2020)	0.10 secs	30
Pandemic declared	March 11 th 2020	WHO , Geneva Cucinotta, ,and Vanelli (2020)	3.11	48.14
Variants, (Data from European Centre for Disease Control (ECDC . 2022) Update frequent, so dates may change				
Alpha*	September 2020	United Kingdom	9.07	49.21
Beta VOC	September 2020	South Africa	9.07	49.21
Gamma VOC	December 2020	Brazil	12.17	49.5
Delta** VOC	December 2020	India	12,17	49.5
Omicron*** VOC	November 2021	South Africa Botswana	23	50.15
It has been called COVID 19, December 2019 is taken as the start, * Alpha – deescalated variant , ** Deltas exalted virulence , April May 2021 (Seetharaman, S & S. Kevany.. 2021) *** Omicron in circulation globally, .VOC = Variants of concern; Alpha, Beta, Gamma, Delta , Omicron				

4.0 Discussion on 2.2: Temperature effect on mutability with reference to delta and other variants.

According to the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control, an agency of the European Union, the delta variant was detected in India in December 2020 (ECDC, 2022); However, the lethal potential of the delta variant was between April to June 2021. A report mentions the mutant delta variant resulted in the deaths of 209,182 people from April 15 to June 17, 2021, in India, with deaths in February below 3000, by March it had increased to over 5000 and by April it has increased 10 fold to 50,000. (Seetharaman and Kevany 2021). December 2020, when the delta variant was detected, was winter in India. As months advance towards April 2021, winter declines, and the temperature rises. $T+10$ in equation (2) becomes a reality. $T+10$ need not be a 10 deg rise. It can be from 2 to 10 deg C or even more. Schrodinger's premise based on equation (2) on mutability increasing as temperature increases with time of expectation of mutation drastically reduced comes into play. It is probable that the rise in temperature between February and April resulting in increased lethal mutability of delta variant could have contributed to increase in deaths.

Schrodinger further states that this is tested for the fly Drosophila in the temperature range which the insects will stand.. Can the test results of Drosophila be extended to COVID 19 and its variants ?. It is probable that one can extend the test results of Drosophila to delta and other variants since the surface area of variants (nanosized or less) would be large enough for enhancing levels of mutability with a temperature rise.. Schrodinger writes another interesting statement “temperature influences unstable genes less than stable ones” to this $T+10$ increase in equation (2). There are a number of questions to be asked.. First,“ Was there a mixed precursor of a gene pool of SARS COV-2 composition right from the start of Delbruck ratio $30@ t = 0.10$ second,. Second, was it a mix of less stable, medium stable, and highly stable genes with highly stable genes mutating to delta variant evolving to a fully blown lethal delta variant in the Indian summer of April to June 2021. There is another aspect to be raised here. Variants roaming around the globe were being subjected to seasonal variations. By equation (2), a variant may have different lethal potential (due to fully blown mutability) when it is winter in the Northern hemisphere (Dec-Jan) and summer in the Southern hemisphere (same Dec-Jan). The reason for these questions is due to different variants produced in many parts of the globe leading to “ terrible times through all-weather seasons” for the human populace.

The present omicron variant appeared at Delbruck ratio 50.15 (23 months) [See Table 1] as December 2019 is considered as the beginning of the pandemic ($t = 0.10$ secs) (Zhu, Wei and Pine 2020). Here we refer to lines from page 41 in the book, under the heading "*The necessity of mutations being a rare event*". The lines "*If they (mutations) were so frequent that there was a considerable chance of, say, a dozen of different mutations occurring in the same individual, the injurious ones would, as a rule, predominate over the advantageous ones and the species, instead of being improved by selection, would remain unimproved, or would perish*". The omicron variant according to reports is heavily mutated, similar to the statement of Schrodinger "a dozen different mutations occurring in the same individual" (Callaway, 2021). There is speculation that the omicron variant will lead the globe from the pandemic becoming endemic. There is caution on the word endemic with the title "Covid 19: endemic doesn't mean harmless" (Katzourakis, 2022) However, a question remains. "Will variants improve by selection or perish , between a Delbruck ratio of 50.3 and 50.4, corresponding to 27 and 29.8 months (as in Table 1) ?

5.0 Conclusion.

There have been significant advances in biological sciences since the book "What is Life "was first published seventy-seven (eight) years ago (1944). However, the search for relevance in "What is Life" to present times of COVID 19 mutations and variants reveals the necessity of early pandemic alertness by preventing lift (threshold energy) from exceeding average heat energy resulting in a significant increase in Delbruck ratio (18.14). A diminished t and an increased mutability is mentioned for fly *Drosophila* in the book with a rise in temperature. A question for experts. Is this applicable to the present mutants and variants of coronaviruses? Finally , how relevant is this study?

6.0 Appendix:

1) The reference of Polyani and Wigner (1928)

- a) Here is the reference mentioned in book to the work of Polanyi M and Wigner E (1928) [Zeitschrift Fuer Physikalische Chemie 1928-12: Vol 139 : Free Download, Borrow, and Streaming : Internet Archive](#). The text is in German. The equation here is as follows.

$$x = \nu e^{-\frac{Q}{RT}} \quad (3)$$

where x = Rate constant : Q = Activation heat : ν = frequencies of atomic oscillation. R is the Gas constant ; T is Absolute temperature. This is similar to Arrhenius equation

$$k = A e^{-\frac{E}{RT}} \quad (4)$$

where k = Rate constant ; A is exponential factor , E_a is the activation energy: R and T , gas constant and absolute temperature Schrodinger uses the work of Polyani and Winger to analogously arrive at the time of expectation of mutation $t = \tau e^{W/KT}$ (1) with Q/RT from equation (3) replaced by $\frac{W}{KT}$ the Delbruck ratio (Dimensionless 30 to 60) . For active heat or activation energy , W the lift is considered with RT being replaced by KT . K is the Boltzmann constant and T the absolute temperature, Note $\frac{W}{KT}$ is positive for exponential growth of t , unlike $-\frac{Q}{RT}$

- b) Choosing τ the small constant as 10^{-14} and not 10^{-13} secs . Choosing 10^{-13} . , gives $t = 1.068$ secs and 16 years for Delbruck ratio of 30 and 50 by equation (1). 10^{-14} gives near about the values as mentioned in the book with a difference that can be ignored. (See Table 1 and 2)

Postscript.

This work has been done based on the chemical technology background of the presenter.. An expert on mutations would be better placed to explain how Delbruck ratios (30 to 60) are obtained and use this preprint to add rigour and later submit for peer review to a journal.

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